

Appendix A. Imports from Japan to overseas destinations, 1955–2025

A.1 Scope and methodology

This appendix lists all currently documented imports of Japanese Spitz dogs from Japan to destinations outside Japan worldwide, grouped chronologically. Dates shown as YYYY.MM.DD represent the dog's date of birth. In most cases, import occurred when the dog was a puppy; therefore, overseas registration in the destination kennel club typically appears in the same calendar year or the following year.

Evidence standard for inclusion: each import entry is verified by at least one of the following: (a) a registration number in the destination country's national stud book; (b) a pedigree certificate showing Japan as the country of birth with a destination-country registration; or (c) corroborating entries in official kennel club online databases (Koiranet, Hunddata, Hundeweb, DogWeb, LOF Select, ENCI Online Stud Book). The Reg.Number column records the destination country's registration identifier, serving as the primary verification reference.

The Nr. Puppies column records the number of registered offspring produced in the destination country, where this information is available from online registry databases. "Unk." indicates that breeding outcome could not be confirmed from available public sources; this does not imply the dog did not breed. Puppies produced via international matings (e.g., semen export or matings performed outside the destination registry system) are not distinguished in these counts.

No claimed imports have been excluded from this list. The 57 entries represent all imports the authors have been able to verify to date. The list is expected to be updated in future versions as additional archival evidence is identified.

A.2 Export registry

Nr	DOB	Name	Sex	Reg_Number	Country	Nr_Puppies
1	1967.03.10	Sabina of Moon Light	F	00011/77	Norway	0
2	1973.01.21	Daniel Of Rose Garden	F	S53972/73	Sweden	21
3	1973.03.28	Andoleason of Golden Meadow	M	S53973/73	Sweden	20
4	1973.05.17	Götter-Mahls Shanshan	M	S53994/73	Sweden	52
5	1973.07.08	Gradice of House Cactus	F	S31141/74	Sweden	7
6	1973.08.11	Athena Leilani of Aloha Land	F	S63169/73	Sweden	8
7	1973.12.20	White Pearl of Lone Hill	F	S22053/74	Sweden	21
8	1975.04.22	Albares Carp of Nedory	M	S32120/76	Sweden	0
9	1975.06.15	Albert of Lovely	M	S32121/76	Sweden	19
10	1975.07.28	Bullet Fancy of Nedory	F	S32119/76	Sweden	15
11	1975.08.05	I.F. Birdie of Tamana Ariakesow	F	S64776/76	Sweden	10
12	1975.08.14	Dick of Nadeshiko Land	M	S64779/76	Sweden	3
13	1975.10.15	Bilke of Summit Field	M	S44456/76	Sweden	25
14	1975.11.05	Hawk Of Kagetsu Land	M	S64778/76	Sweden	113

15	1975.11.05	Hover of Kagetsu Land	M	S44457/76	Sweden	47
16	1975.11.16	Adela of Amage	F	S64777/76	Sweden	16
17	1975.11.16	Alice of Amage	F	S44455/76	Sweden	17
18	1975.12.05	Florence Of Rose Garden	F	00242/75	Norway	3
19	1977.02.26	Fujimiland Baby Ramale	M	S37306/78	Sweden	72
20	1977.06.14	White Joanna Of Moon Light	F	S13492/79	Sweden	32
21	1979.07.04	Gaia of Tamana Ariakesow	F	S28142/80	Sweden	19
22	1979.07.05	Hannah of Tamana Ariakesow	F	S28143/80	Sweden	21
23	1979.07.05	Harry of Tamana Ariakesow	M	S28140/80	Sweden	22
24	1979.07.13	Axel of Kobe Manamisow	M	S28141/80	Sweden	17
25	1980.12.10	Alex of Golden Meadow	M	S50707/81	Sweden	19
26	1980.12.31	Fuji Of Oyama Yamamotosow	M	SP-274/81	UK	3
27	1981.06.28	Jingle Bell of Harima Takeda	M	S18103/82	Sweden	2
28	1981.06.29	Idol of Nadeshiko Land	M	S18102/82	Sweden	6
29	1983.02.04	Shirayuki of Tokyo Seizansow	F	SP-272/83	UK	10
30	1983.09.10	Agree of Senbon Matsubarasow	M	S15264/85	Sweden	11
31	1984.11.12	Take-Maru of Yokohama Takada	M	048029/86	Italy	Unk.
32	1984.11.12	Take-Oh of Yokohama Takada	M	05461/85	Denmark	56
33	1984.11.11	Agree of Ooka Hiyoshisow	F	NSA26-5765/85	Italy	0
34	1987.04.12	Fujiko Of White Kodamasow	F	086394/89	Italy	0
35	1992.06.18	Masamitsu Of Yokohama Murata	M	055801/95	Italy	Unk.
36	1994.02.07	Boby of Koza Land	M	SP-00977/99	UK	2
37	1997.05.24	Eren Hof Fudziana San Vom Rollenden Haus	M	RKF 0000012	Russia	Unk.
38	2002.03.12	Ostara of M Early Summer	F	S56574/2002	Sweden	5
39	2002.10.05	Ryuuchi Of Maruko Nomura	M	CBKC A1947	Brazil	Unk.
40	2003.04.27	Accel Of God Mount	M	FIN42473/03	Finland	30
41	2003.07.24	Spitz Paradise Angel Mito	M	RKF 1584522	Russia	Unk.
42	2004.03.10	Prize Of Matsushimosato	M	LOF 120/22	France	39
43	2004.02.04	Kotohime Of Shonan Sumiresow	F	LOI04/94759	Italy	Unk.
44	2005.10.22	Kikuchiyo Of Shonan Sumiresow	M	LOI04/94774	Italy	10
45	2005.10.22	Shonan Sumiresow Sayako	F	FIN21483/06	Finland	1
46	2005.11.18	Jin-Cherry Jp Emily	F	CBKC A1946	Brazil	Unk.
47	2005.12.17	New Tokyo Kennel's Joddy	M	SE60993/2011	Sweden	11
48	2006.01.25	Branly Of Casablanca Tomo	F	CBKC A1945	Brazil	Unk.
49	2006.09.02	Naomi Of Konparu Wakata	F	FIN57457/07	Finland	10
50	2007.06.26	Lapilazuli Of Sylph Sato	M	FIN28402/08	Finland	47
51	2008.05.05	Spitz Paradise Angel Aki	M	RKF2334801	Russia	Unk.
52	2008.06.05	Ikar Of Hondasow	M	RKF 2334800	Russia	Unk.
53	2008.11.26	Orange Hill Doris	F	FI59538/09	Finland	24

54	2013.09.12	Million Steeps White Chouchou	F	JKCSP00601/13	Norway	11
55	2018.03.16	Eren Hof Hamahime	F	SE54267/2018	Sweden	9
56	2018.04.06	Eren Hof Fujiyama	M	SE54266/2018	Sweden	9
57	2024.12.24	Eren Hof Hanku	M	LOF 5078/337	France	0

A.3 Summary by destination and decade

Decade	Sweden	Norway	UK	Italy	Finland	France	Russia	Brazil	Denmark	Total
1960s	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
1970s	22	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23
1980s	4	0	2	3	0	0	0	0	1	10
1990s	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	3
2000s	2	0	0	2	5	1	3	3	0	16
2010s	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
2020s	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
Total	30	3	3	6	5	2	4	3	1	57

Sweden received the majority of exports (30 of 57 dogs), reflecting its role as the primary gateway for the breed's expansion into the FCI system beginning in 1973. Pedigree analysis (Section 6.1) confirms that many Swedish-bound exports were closely related: the single sire Paul of Sagami Kubota produced 6 of 30 Swedish imports, and Floyd Excel of Tokyo Kashusow sired 3 more, together accounting for over one-third of Sweden's founder cohort.

A.4 Pedigree-verified relatedness among exports

Pedigree data identifying 44 unique sires and 49 unique dams. The following table summarizes the six confirmed full-sibling groups:

Group	Dogs	Sire	Dam	Type	Puppies
1	#14 Hawk + #15 Hover	Floyd Excel of Tokyo Kashusow	Animete of Makiesow	Same litter	160
2	#16 Adela + #17 Alice	Paul of Sagami Kubota	Vicky of Tamana Ariakesow	Same litter	33
3	#22 Hannah + #23 Harry	Paul of Sagami Kubota	Margaret of Tamana Ariakesow	Same litter	43
4	#31 Take-Maru + #32 Take-Oh	Alcyon of Port Masuda	Asa-giku of Mischief Queen	Same litter	56+
5	#43 Kotohime, #44 Kikuchiyo, #45 Sayako	Qualtee of Star Murohoshi	Haruna of Nadeshiko Land	Litter + repeat	11

6	#41 Mito + #50 Aki	Gaily of Kanto Pigeon White	Cammy Angel of Rose Paradise	Repeat mating	Unk.
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Beyond full siblings, pedigree analysis reveals extensive half-sibling networks through shared sires:

Shared sire	Exports	Unique dams	Combined puppies
Paul of Sagami Kubota	6 (#16, #17, #21, #22, #23, #11)	4	105
Floyd Excel of Tokyo Kashusow	3 (#9, #14, #15)	2	179
Qualtee of Star Murohoshi	3 (#43, Kotohime, #44)	1	11
Catharine of Shirakawa Noguchi	2 (#8, #10)	2	15
Excel Egret of Lilac Spring	2 (#6, #5)	2	15
Gaily of Kanto Pigeon White	2 (#41, #50)	1	Unk.
Alcyon of Port Masuda	2 (#31, #32)	1	56+

One maternal half-sibling pair was also confirmed: Daniel (#2) and Florence (#18) of Rose Garden share the dam Rommy of Rose Garden but have different sires. Connected-component analysis identifies 8 multi-dog relatedness clusters containing 22 dogs, plus 35 singletons with no detected parental overlap, yielding an effective founder diversity of approximately 50 independent genetic contributions (88% of the 57 pedigreed imports).

A.5 Verification sources

1. Finnish Kennel Club — KoiraNet Breeding Database
2. Swedish Kennel Club — Hunddata Registry
3. Danish Kennel Club — Hundeweb Database
4. Norwegian Kennel Club — DogWeb Database
5. Italian Kennel Club (ENCI) — Online Stud Book
6. Société Centrale Canine (France) — LOF Select
7. The Kennel Club (UK) — Health Test Results Finder